

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the third regular issue in 2015. We are proud and happy to announce that the recently published impact factor for 2014 of the journal has risen as compared to 2013. The impact factor is now 0.466, the 5-year impact factor is 0.566. I'd like to thank all members of our editorial board for their review efforts which guarantee the quality of the published papers. My thanks go also to the J.UCS consortium for its substantial support.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce 5 accepted papers from 6 different countries.

The authors Christophe Costa Florêncio, Jonny Daenen, Jan Ramon, Jan Van den Bussche, and Dries Van Dyck from Belgium report their research considering the naive bottom-up concatenation scheme for a context-free language and show that this scheme has the incremental polynomial time property. Yasmín Hernández, Gustavo Arroyo-Figueroa, and L. Enrique Sucar from Mexico introduce their model of affect and learning to be applied to intelligent tutor systems. Angela Mendoza, Susana Mata, and Luis Pastor from Spain present their novel approach for visualizing neurons directly from the morphological descriptions extracted by neuroscience laboratories to improve the readability of complex neuronal scenarios and to avoid the need to store 3D models of the intricate geometry. In the collaborative research between UK and Ireland, Andreea Molnar and Cristina Hava Muntean focus on the influence of learning achievements when reducing mobile video quality. Jose Luis Santos, Katrien Verbert, Joris Klerkx, Sven Charleer, Erik Duval, and Stefaan Ternier present in a collaborative work between Belgium and the Netherlands an architecture for collecting and managing learning traces in open learning environments.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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